

wasteless

Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress

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D7.3 – DEC Plan - Update

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VIMOSZ	18/06/2024	WP7 contributions implemented, and draft sent to internal review WP1, SDU.	V0.3
IFA	27/06/2024	Internal review contributions implemented, final review by WP leader, and draft sent to Coordinator.	V0.4
UTAD	28/06/2024	Final review, approval, and submission to the E.C	V1.0

Executive Summary

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan – Update (D7.3) is the update of D7.2 at M18, and includes: (1) a progress report of what has been done during the first 18 months of the project, (2) an amendment of the DEC Plan where necessary (e.g., a YouTube channel added to the communication platforms, updated website description, etc.) and (3) an evaluation of the DEC activities to enhance project operations where needed. All this in line with the framework of the DEC Plan.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AAFC	Association of Agricultural and Food Cooperatives
CoP	Community of Practice
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EN	English
EU	European Union
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
H&FS&R	Hospitality and Food Services and Retailers
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
KSP	Knowledge Sharing Platform
M	Month
MS	Member States
NA	Not applicable
N/R	National and/or Regional
SoMe	Social media
WP	Work Package
T&M	Tools and Methodologies

1. Introduction: Progress of DEC activities at M18

To expand WASTELESS impact the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan (D7.2) was created at M6 as a support document to build the project's DEC strategy and the roadmap to put it in place. It is used to make the results public (dissemination), to make concrete use of the results achieved (exploitation) and to promote the project and its results (communication).

A strong visual identity and a virtual ecosystem was created during the first 18 months of the project. So far, the focus has been on communication, e.g. by raising awareness about the project aims, creating a strong community, building the project's brand, and reaching target groups while dissemination is still in the initial phase (5 scientific articles published) as project results are starting to be collected only gradually, and exploitation didn't start yet.

Communication about the project has been successful according to the Key Performance Indicators as defined in D7.2 (annex I). The highlight of this period is the high number of people reached by the consortium, according to the KPIs, which in some cases is already ahead of the target number by many folds. There are target audiences that were hard to reach albeit those groups are best reached when more project results are generated. Therefore, an updated estimation reach was needed.

The project has also created another communication platform, [YouTube](#) where several activities take place. By M18 the WASTELESS YouTube has published: (1) the project video, (2) three videos of the Tools and Methodologies (T&M), (3) three livestreams of the Monthly Café Talks, and (4) four livestreams of topic sessions of the joint webinar with the sister project FOLLOU. So far, the Youtube channel has more than 600 views.

Exploitation, i.e., making concrete use of the results, has not yet started and will begin towards the end of the project, as soon as the project has exploitable results and will continue beyond its end. Exploitation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Strategy will be written as a deliverable report (D7.6) due M36 by the team of Task 7.4. This task will start at M25 and at this stage Task 7.4 leaders are involved in the WPs that deliver the project results (WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6), manage data collection and integration (WP4) and attend regular WPs meetings.

All the activities that were carried out during this period were in line with the DEC Plan (D7.2) and this update (D7.3) will be again updated in the final report (D7.4) due M36.

2. Target groups and engagement

WASTELESS is focusing on the multi-actor approach to transform food systems with the final aim of reducing FLW at different stages of the food chain. In the DEC Plan target audiences were defined with target reach. In this section a thorough description of the progress will be given as well as an analysis of each target audience. An estimated reach of the target audiences is presented (Table 1) based on the numbers extracted from the project's Community of Practice (CoP), YouTube channel and DEC reporting by M18, website, LinkedIn and X channels by M17. The estimation is challenging as from different analytics and reports we get a general estimation of followers, visits, etc and only the CoP, though registered members provide information about their affiliation and activity sector. Table 1 includes also the challenges encountered to reach the specific target group as well as measures to be implemented in the future to improve the communication and dissemination activities towards the group.

Table 1. Updated estimated reach of target audiences, challenges and measures

Target audience	Estimated reach		Challenges	Measures
	(M18)	(M36)		
European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies	0 EU policymakers 5 N/R policymakers 3 Food Agencies (2) national (1) private (0) FLW quantification	14 National Agencies or responsible organisations for FLW quantification and reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language barriers • Low contribution of project partners • Generation of results is in the initial phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of local languages • Engagement of project partners through communication with local target audience • WP leaders' regular meetings
Civil Society (organisations/associations)	17 Trade associations 0 AAFC 0 Consumer organisations	25 Trade and Consumer organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of results is in the initial phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase dissemination with the generation of results • Draft a list targeting AAFC and consumer organisations
European, national, and regional private sector	16 Private companies 0 H&FS&R	30 H&FS&R	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of results is in the initial phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on dissemination in the later stage of the project • Draft a list targeting H&FS&R
Scientific community	61 universities and research institutes	30 universities and research institutes	NA	NA
General public	++3000 consumers	3000 consumers	NA	NA
Other research projects and initiatives	18 similar projects	20 similar projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find activities of common interest for collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion of new projects funded in the next calls

2.1 European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies

Policymakers and food agencies from all over Europe are responsible for providing strategies and establishing high standards for all actors of the value chain. They are a key target of this project, as the focus is both on the public food system and on the private one. Local authorities (governments, city councils but also specific agencies, bodies, etc.) will be directly involved in the consultations to jointly define FLW challenges. Testimonials of these local policymakers will be collected in WP1 and WP4. Further, WASTELESS will provide them a set of standards for the tested tools as well as recommendations for a future regulatory framework for FLW reduction.

Estimated reach: 30 National Agencies or responsible organisations for FLW quantification and reporting.

For the analysis of the target audience reached the categories of this group were clearly defined as:

(1) *Policymakers* - a person who is responsible for or involved in developing plans of action for a political party, business, etc. at EU, national or regional (N/R) level; (2) *National agencies* - national public-sector bodies, or bodies governed by private law with a public-service mission; (3) *Private agencies* – body represented by a person, partnership, corporation or association that is not public agency, whether financed in whole or in part by public funds

In all categories only those related to the food sector were considered and within these the ones responsible for FLW quantification and reporting were also identified.

According to the CoP at M18 the following were reached (Table 1): 5 policymakers all at N/R level (0 at EU level), 3 food agencies of which 2 national (Austria and Estonia) agencies, and 1 private food agency (Austria). Among them none is responsible for FLW quantification and reporting.

European policymakers are still missing, and the numbers of national agencies are low considering that we are halfway through the project and no organisations responsible for FLW quantification and reporting were reached. However, some might have been reached through the activities done by the project partners through their network, but it is difficult to estimate.

The National agencies responsible for FLW quantification and reporting included in D1.2 were contacted through emails (85), however no positive interactions could be set. The language barrier is being considered a concerning issue. The WP7 team is counting on the contribution of consortium members to engage with national food agencies responsible for FLW quantification and reporting, in their own language in the next months, and thus it is expected to reach at least the national agencies from the 14 countries involved in the project. Also, once WASTELESS produces more results, these agencies and organisations will be much easier to reach.

Updated estimated reach: 14 National Agencies or responsible organisations for FLW quantification and reporting.

2.2 Civil Society (organisations/associations)

The Civil Society mentioned here includes European and National Food Industry Trade Associations, the Association of Agricultural and Food Cooperatives and Consumer organisations from partner countries and all over Europe. Their members are important beneficiaries of the outcomes of WASTELESS, as they face or will face the negative impact of uncontrolled FLW on their quality of life. Bottom-up approaches

will ensure the inclusion of the views of local communities in WASTELESS strategies, to get a clear picture of FLW measurement needs and challenges and to jointly co-design possible solutions. Engaging with the civil society organisations will increase the number of consumers reached.

Estimated reach: 50 Trade and Consumer organisations.

For the analysis of the target audience reached the categories of this group were clearly defined as:

(1) *Food Industry Trade Associations* - organisations founded and funded by food & beverages businesses that operate in a specific industry. They usually participate in public relation activities such as advertising, education, political donations, lobbying and publishing, and focusing on collaboration between companies; (2) *Association of Agricultural and Food Cooperatives (AAFC)* - agricultural and food organisations which are owned and run jointly by its members, who share the profits and benefits; (3) *Consumer organisations* - membership-based non-governmental non-profit body created to promote the interests of consumers of goods and services, by disseminating information and lobbying for laws to protect consumers against producers or sellers, who may usually be better organised or have more resources.

By M18, 17 Food Industry Trade Associations, 0 AAFC and 0 Consumer organisations have been reached through the CoP (Table 1). As generation of results is still in the initial phase, once more results are available, the dissemination towards this target group will be enhanced. WP7 will draft in the next month a list targeting AAFC and consumer organisations and together with the project partners will invite them to be part of the CoP and activities organised

Updated Estimated reach: 25 Trade and Consumer organisations.

2.3 European, national, and regional private sector

Private companies in the food sector (producers, processors, distributors, and retailers) are affected by FLW, and thus constitute a target audience for WASTELESS. By having proper measurement and monitoring tools, as well as strategies to reduce FLW, they can lower their economic costs and negative environmental impacts. English (EN) language will be used and prioritised, however translations to other EU languages can be done if necessary or if needed by the partners.

Estimated reach: 300 hospitality & food services and retailers.

Sixteen private companies in the food sector were reached so far, mostly food producers and distribution. Hospitality & Food Services and Retailers (H&FS&R) were not reached (Table 1). This number will increase in the future, along with the development of the case studies. Nevertheless, it is currently unforeseeable to reach the target number set in D7.2. A more realistic estimate would be a lower number, taking in consideration that we are halfway through the project and case studies are in its development phase, we foreseen to reach 30 H&FS&R.

Update estimated reach: 30 hospitality & food services and retailers.

2.4 Scientific community

Researchers working on measuring, monitoring, and reducing FLW are an important target audience of the project. WASTELESS will inform researchers on perceived system dynamics, priorities, and perceived impacts, and will establish a place for collaboration and networking. Scientific evidence on

harmonized measuring and monitoring of FLW and on innovative processes and streams to valorise unavoidable FLW will boost innovation uptake.

Estimated reach: 30 universities and research institutes.

So far 61 universities and research institutions have been reached through the CoP (Table 1) but this number is much higher looking to the registrants affiliations of Monthly Café Talks and the Webinar held in the last months. This kind of institutions are more open to innovation than others, therefore it is possible to reach in higher numbers though the lifetime of the project.

2.5 General public

Consumers are central to achieving food waste reduction. WASTELESS is providing a common space for citizens to engage in joint decision-making with producers, retailers, and policymakers through its website and Community of Practice. Consumers are a major driver for change and through active engagement WASTELESS will provide information about the main causes of food waste at the consumer level, the monitoring tools developed, and strategies needed to reach responsible consumption. Citizens will be invited to discover the WASTELESS methodology, tools and toolbox, as well as results, and will be encouraged to participate in the policy-making process. English language will be used but translations to other EU languages included in the project are also predicted. WASTELESS must ensure the continuity of the activities and the mid-and long-term sustainability of its results once the EU funding comes to an end. Thus, the project will seek connections between the local community and private and public food system stakeholders.

Estimated reach: 3000 consumers.

Generally, it is hard to give a good estimation of this target group as they can be reached through many types of activities and channels. Although the CoP by M18 has 126 members the real impact is much higher: (i) the CoP also has 25 FLW experts engaged in its activities and only 4 are registered members, (ii) LinkedIn counts on 523 followers, X with 179 followers and YouTube with 21 subscribers, (iii) based on the traffic registered on the website 590k visits were reached by M17, and finally (iv) counting also the network of the consortium (direct reach of the consortium members, sister projects etc.), more than 38k people were reached by M18 according to the KPIs (Annex I). With these numbers included, the project has significantly overachieved itself in this target group.

2.6 Other research projects and initiatives

Past, current, and upcoming FLW regional, national, European, and international projects and initiatives will be identified to leverage collaboration. The aim is to support user community interactions and research, to avoid duplication of efforts and to maximize exploitation of FLW measurement tools and reduction actions. WASTELESS will define synergies, enhance the acceptability and visibility of the outcomes, and foster their uptake.

Estimated reach: 20 coordinators of similar projects and initiatives.

Nineteen coordinators or communication leaders of similar projects and initiatives have been reached including the sister project. Nine projects were reached by email and 8 accepted to collaborate, sister project was reached through the project officer, 5 projects were reached through partners and other 4 projects though the projects already in our network.

In total 18 projects (Table 2) are now part of our collaboration network of which 14 are already present on the WASTELESS website. We almost reached the target at M18 and by the end of the project we will probably overachieve the reach, counting on the new projects which will be funded through future EU calls and the ongoing collaborations.

Table 2. Projects in collaboration with WASTELESS

Project	Full title	Funding scheme	End date
FOLOU	Bringing knowledge and consensus to prevent and reduce food loss at the primary production stage. Understanding, measuring, training and adopting	HORIZON	31/12/2026
BREADCRUMB	BRinging Evidence-bAseD food Chain solutions to prevent and RedUce food waste related to Marketing standards, and deliver climate and circularity co-Benefits	HORIZON	31/12/2027
CORENET	Connecting advisOrs towaRd a European NETwork for consumer-producer chains	HORIZON	14/09/2027
CULTIVATE	Co-designing food sharing innovation for food resilience	HORIZON	31/12/2026
TONOWASTE	Towards a new zero food waste mindset based on holistic assessment	HORIZON	31/08/2026
CHORIZO	Changing practices and habits through Open, responsible, and social Innovation towards zero food waste	HORIZON	30/09/2025
BIORECER	Biological Resources Certifications Schemes	HORIZON	31/08/2025
SISTERS	Systemic innovations for a sustainable reduction of the European food wastage	H2020	30/04/2026
BBTWINS	Agri-Food value chain digitalization for resource efficiency	H2020	31/05/2025
LOWINFOOD	Evaluating selected innovations for food waste reduction in the EU	H2020	28/02/2025
ZeroW	Innovations for Zero Food Loss & Waste	H2020	2025
Waste2Func	Lactic acid and biosurfactants sourced from sustainable agricultural and industrial (food) WASTE feedstocks as novel functional ingredients for consumer products	H2020	30/11/2024
FOODRUS	Circular solutions for resilient food systems	H2020	30/04/2024
Model2BIO	Modelling tool for giving value to agri-food residual streams in bio-based industries	H2020	31/10/2023
NewFeed	Turn food industry by-products into secondary feedstuffs via circular-economy schemes	PRIMA	30/06/2025
Nano4Fresh	Nanomaterials for an environmentally friendly and sustainable handling of perishable products	PRIMA	30/11/2023
FoodLoops	Local Cooperation for Circular Biowaste in Schools and Beyond	Interreg	06/2025
WASTELESS (Maradék nélkül)	National food waste prevention programme in Hungary	EU LIFE + National	-----

3. Dissemination and communication channels and tools

3.1 Project Visual Identity

This section outlines the progress made on the visual identity and dissemination materials for the WASTELESS project. Our efforts focused on creating a cohesive and recognizable brand for the project, in alignment with the requirements set forth in the project description. The visual identity components, including the brand book, logo, templates, and other dissemination materials, have been successfully created and made available to all partners.

3.1.1. Logo and branding

EuroFIR and VIMOSZ have developed the visual identity of the WASTELESS project. The following components have been created and are accessible to all partners:

- Project Brand Book: A comprehensive guide detailing the visual identity, including colour schemes, typography, logo usage, and branding guidelines.
- Logo: The official logo of the WASTELESS project has been designed and is included in all relevant materials.
- Templates: Standardized templates for presentations and reports have been created and uploaded to the project's intranet (Google Drive).
- The background to be used in online meetings

These elements are prominently displayed on all DEC materials, project website, social media channels, and partners' communication tools. The visual identity adheres to the HORIZON program guidelines, ensuring a professional and consistent appearance across all platforms.

3.1.2. Leaflet, poster, roll-up, video, goodies

The following materials have been created and distributed, while some items have been intentionally excluded due to sustainability.

- Leaflet: A project leaflet, detailing an overview of the project, objectives, partners, and communication channels, has been created in PDF format. It is available on the project website and GDrive for partners to download and print as needed.
- Roll-up: A roll-up banner design has been prepared and is accessible in PDF format on the intranet.
- Promotional video: The first promotional video, approximately 2 minutes long, has been produced and launched, presenting the project, its objectives, partners, case studies, and expected outcomes. The second video will be developed and released by M34 to showcase the project results.

The goodies (type and numbers) will be decided by each partner depending on the event and type of audience and will be designed using the project's brand book. WP7 can provide support, as necessary.

3.2 Virtual performance

3.2.1 Website

The project [Website](https://wastelesseu.com) (domain wastelesseu.com) was developed by VIMOSZ and was officially launched in March 2023 (M3). It enhances the visibility and communication about the project by including information about the project itself, the partners of the consortium, project results (including the tools

and methods developed, guidelines, etc.), news and upcoming events, case studies, blog posts related to FLW, other relevant links and information and more. Other resources (e.g., trainings) will be added according to the project development. The structure of the website has been changed compared to what was reported in D 7.7, to agree with the development of the project (e.g., inclusion of the CoP). At M18, the website structure consists of the following pages and subpages: Home, About, Entities (Partners, Advisory board), Outcomes (Tools, Case studies, Publications), Community (Blog, Trainings, Newsroom, Tools, Publications, Networking), Knowledge Sharing Platform and Contact. The following is included on all pages: EU funding acknowledgment, Copyrights as well as different tabs to access other information. The website will be maintained for at least three years after the project ends to ensure its sustainability and VIMOSZ will be the responsible partner. The website was described in detail in the [deliverable 7.7 Website and social media](#) (M3).

3.2.2 Social media

The SoMe accounts [LinkedIn](#) and [X](#), have been created and by M17, a good proportion of the project's online communication was done on LinkedIn (156 posts) and X (131 posts). The project has built a strong community on both platforms, which is represented in the KPIs (Annex I). The type of audience on the SoMe platform is difficult to establish. According to the LinkedIn analytics the followers are mainly working in research and education 30% and food and beverages industry 16%.

Based on the project needs, a [YouTube](#) channel was created later (M16) and is used to disseminate video materials including project video, tools presentation, records of the Monthly Café talks, Webinars, etc. The main advantage of YouTube is that it offers the possibility to add subtitles in many languages increasing the impact towards local actors. KPIs were included for the YouTube channel in Annex I. The channel was created and will be managed by VIMOSZ.

3.2.3. Knowledge sharing platform

WASTELESS is using the [Sustainable Food Systems Innovation Platform](#) as an online environment to share knowledge on food systems and raise awareness about the project among different stakeholders. WASTELESS is one of the projects managing (through IFA) the platform and is involved in its regular updates. WASTELESS contributed to the improvement of the platform which now has a new home page and new features like a live X feed, automatic translation to 100+ languages and the latest inventory addition feed. The platform hosts 6 inventories which can be browsed or searched or filtered in multiple ways. WASTELESS Case Studies, videos, scientific publications are already added to the platform inventory and will be regularly updated through the development of the project. The CoP was also added in the Community section. The platform is described in detail in D7.1 - Knowledge sharing platforms for food systems (due M18).

3.2.4. Community of practice

The CoP is part of the WP1 and includes among others European and National Food Industry Trade Associations, Association of Agricultural and Food Cooperatives, and National Food Agencies from every European Member State (MS) has been established (Task 1.4). The CoP fosters the exchange of views and adoption of best practice on FLW measuring and monitoring strategies, for their harmonization, and promotes collaboration and networking between competent authorities. It will be used to publicize project policy recommendations. The results will be reported in D1.4 CoP and replication at MS level (due M36).

The CoP is part of the WASTELESS website. The activities in the CoP include blog articles (34), news and events (27), as well as publications (11). It facilitates collaboration and networking among the members and will offer e-learnings in the future. Monthly Café Talks (until M18, 3 have been organised and more are planned for this year), round table events (1 in M18 and 1 more planned for M30) and evaluation of tools developed under the project by external experts are also part of the CoP.

3.2.5. e-learning platform

The development of the trainings is at M18 in the initial phase, including interviews with representatives of actors involved in the Case Studies and mapping of existing training to identify the needs of the target groups in respect to content and structure of future training.

3.2.6. Zenodo community

All WASTELESS publications are being published in the [Zenodo](#) community which counts at M18 with 11 records (5 scientific publications, 2 other publications, 4 videos) summing 91 views and 79 downloads.

3.3. Publications, articles, and media dissemination

3.3.1. Blog

The Blog section on the WASTELESS website is part of the CoP and is filled with articles written by consortium members and external experts. A document providing the methodology and guidelines for the authors and outlining the general requirements for the blog articles was drafted by VIMOSZ and shared with all project partners. The document includes suggested topics, appropriate use of language, citation and the process of submission. The document can be found on the [GDrive](#).

By M18, at the submission date 34 articles have been published on the website, which is in line with the KPIs (Annex I).

3.3.2 Newsletter

Two newsletters have been released: at M6 the [1st newsletter](#), at M12 the [2nd newsletter](#), and the third one will be release by the submission date of this deliverable therefore no analytic data is available yet. The first two newsletters have been sent to an average of 110 subscribers and have an average 34% opens and 7% clicks.

3.3.3 News for the written media, radio, and TV

Two press releases were disseminated: (1) about the launch of the project (M2), translated in Spanish, Slovenian and Turkish, with an estimated reach of 78 people, (2) about the launch of CoP (M10), translated in Portuguese, with an estimated reach of 459 people. The estimated reach was based on the post views on WASTELESS SoMe channels, which is underestimated since it is not counting with the partner's dissemination through their websites, newsletters and SoMe as reported in the DEC Reporting document. Nine news about WASTELESS project such as report updates (M6, M12, M18), surveys, events, workshops and other activities related to the project were written by some partners (UTAD, SDU, IFA, JSI, EUROPATAT) and published in the CoP Newsroom.

3.3.4. Scientific papers and publications in technical magazine

At M18, 5 scientific papers and 2 publications in technical magazines ([Perspetiva magazine](#), [TecnoAlimentar](#)) resulted from the WASTELESS project were published. The scientific publications can be found in the project website, in the Zenodo Community as well as on the SFSI Platform.

3.3.5. Practice abstracts

Practice abstracts are to be developed in WP6, which started at M16. Therefore, the practice abstracts are in an early development phase. More details can be found in D6.2 (due M18).

3.4. Events

WASTELESS has been represented by several project partners by M18 at 13 events (Table 3) and organised 5 of other events (JSI, IFA).

Discussion forum and workshops, trainings and WASTELESS final conference are in development phase to be presented later in the project, more details can be found in D7.2.

Table 3. Participation of WASTELESS partners in events (based on the DEC Reporting document)

No.	Project partner	Name of the event	No. Participants
1	IFA+UTAD	EU platform on FLW monitoring subgroup meeting	100
2	VIMOSZ	FSE General Assembly - WASTELESS Presentation	20
3	UTAD+Colab4Food	Encontro Ciência 2023	(a)
4	IFA	IFA conference	267
5	UTAD	Conferência sobre dieta mediterrânica	(a)
6	FIAB*+CTIC-CITA	Alibetopias	300
7	LVA	annual FIAA (Food Industries Association Austria) welcome fair	250
8	JSI*	Workshop “From food waste to sustainable building solutions” ^Φ	25
9	IFA	Food2030 networking conference	300
10	VIMOSZ	SIRHA Budapest (2024) HoReCa and Retail Show	200
11	SEVT	SEVT's stand in FOOD EXPO fair 2024	+1000
12	LVA	ALIBER Barcelona	35
13	FIAB	Alimentaria Barcelona Fair	+100000
14	FIAB+CTIC-CITA	Expo FoodTech Food4Future	(a)
15	IFA*	Monthly Café Talk April ^Φ	26
16	IFA*	Monthly Café Talk May ^Φ	17
17	IFA*	Monthly Café Talk June ^Φ	11
18	IFA*	Webinar “Current developments in Food Loss & Waste reduction” ^Φ	160

*Organizer; Φ Event part of WASTELESS activities; (a) No information provided

3.5. Partners' own dissemination channels

WASTELESS partners have been active in communicating about WASTELESS project, in particular CTIC-CITA, EUROFIR, EUROPATAT, FIAB, FIPA, IFA, JSI, LVA, SETBIR, SEVT, TARTU BT PARK, UTAD, VIMOSZ and WIISE. By M18, 115 mentions were made in SoMe, press releases, websites, mailing lists, newsletters, meetings, events and others. The estimate reach was more than 38K people through the partners' network.

3.6. Dissemination activities in cooperation with sister project and similar projects

Activities in cooperation with sister project and similar projects by M18 are 8. Most of the projects in collaboration have the logo and brief description of WASTELESS in their websites (1), follow WASTELESS on SoMe channels and WASTELESS follow them and interact with their posts actively (2). WASTELESS is a member of FOODRUS cooperation collaboration network (3) and of the FOOD2030 network (4). A policy statement is being prepared in collaboration with ZeroW, SISTERS and others including the sister project FOLOU, as an update of the [statement published in November 2023](#) (5) and a [joint blog article](#) was written on the Stop Food Waste Day in collaboration with ZeroW, CHORIZO, BREADCRUMB and SISTERS (6). The webinar "Current developments in Food Loss & Waste reduction" was organized jointly with the sister project FOLOU on June 17 and 18, 2024, and the projects ZeroW, TONOWASTE, SISTERS, FOODRUS, CHORIZO, CULTIVATE, LOWINFOOD, FOODLOOPS, NEWFEED, WASTE2FUNC participated as invited speakers. More than 300 people registered for the webinar and 169 attended in the two days (7). WASTELESS coordinator was invited to moderate the topical session that is being organized by FOLOU at the [LCA Food international conference](#) to be held in September 2024 (8).

4. Key project messages

At M6, WASTELESS has defined various key messages, tailored to different target groups and to the channels and tools used to communicate and disseminate them (see table 3 in D7.2). Up until now, the key messages of the project did not change, but 3 new messages were included, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. New key messages tailored to specific target audiences and DC channels and tools selected to circulate them.

Key message	Target audience	Channels and tools
Accurate and consistent data collection and presentation are crucial for understanding food waste trends and implementing effective reduction strategies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all
Comprehensive data capture across the entire food supply chain is essential for understanding and addressing food loss and waste.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policymakers, and food agencies • private sector • Scientific community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all
Evidence-based data is crucial for effective decision-making and targeted interventions to reduce food loss and waste.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all

5. Exploitation Strategy

As described in D7.2 guidelines for the exploitation and IPR strategy will be written by WP7 (JSI) from M25 and will be published at M36, D7.6 - Exploitation and IPR Strategy. To be in line with the development of the project and, specifically the development of tools, the establishment of the exploitation strategy is now in the initial phase and WP7 follows the development of the tools to measure and monitor FLW.

6. Reporting, evaluation, and monitoring of DEC activities

6.1 Reporting

A [DEC Reporting document](#) is being used by all partners to list all activities related to DEC. This document is updated at M18 and overseen by IFA.

6.2. Evaluation

For the evaluation procedure of DEC performance, the KPIs defined in the D7.2 have been updated based on the progress of the project (Annex I).

6.3. Monitoring

IFA and VIMOSZ will oversee the progress of DEC activities regularly by analysing the [DEC Reporting document](#), the KPIs and the overall DEC performance. In case of deviations, VIMOSZ will contact and follow up with the partners in due course. The DEC Plan will be reviewed at M36 when a final report will be provided.

7. Conclusion

D7.3 is the update of the DEC plan (D7.2) at M18. The major output of this deliverable is the progress report of the activities that were defined in the DEC Plan and review of the KPIs accordingly. A project has created a strong visual identity and a virtual ecosystem which can outlive the duration of the WASTELESS project. The DC activities of the project are in line with the KPIs. Although the project is achieving promising numbers in certain target audiences, some are not yet well reached. This is because WASTELESS is just in the initial phase of generating results. With the development of the project the reach of the target audiences should increase and measures to improve were set up.

8. Annexes

8.1 Annex I – Key Performance indicators

KPI	M18	Target at M36	Type of data
Website*			
Nº of visits	5900	3000	Google Analytics
Nº of pages/visit	8.2	3	
Average time spent/visit (min)	2:23	2	
LinkedIn			
Nº of posts*	156	150	Hootsuite Analytics
Nº of followers	523	400	
Page engagement*	2000	1500	
Page clicks*	1300	1500	
X			
Nº of posts*	131	150	Hootsuite Analytics
Nº of followers	179	400	
Post key interactions*	1600	1500	
YouTube			
Nº of videos	11	20	YouTube Analytics
Nº of subscribers	21	50	
Average watch time	1:51 min	3:00 min	
Knowledge sharing platform			
Nº of visits	1450/ month	2500	Google Analytics
Nº of pages/visit	6.5	3	
Average time spent/visit (min)	5.5	2	
E-learning platform			
Nº of courses	0	2	Moodle Analytics
Nº trainees/course	0	10	
Nº of completed trainings	0	10	
Zenodo			
Nº of documents	11	40	Zenodo Analytics
Nº of visits	91	100	
Blog/CoP			
Nº of articles	34	100	Google Analytics
Nº of page visits	1400/year	1500	
Newsletter			
Releases	3	6	Mailchimp Analytics
Nº of subscribers	110	100	
Nº of openings (%)	34	50	

*Numbers refer to M17, numbers for M18 only available on M19

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(Cont.)

KPI	M18	Target at M36	Type of data
News for the written media, radio, and TV			
Nº of press releases	2	3	DEC reporting
Nº of news	9	20	
Nº of people reached	+++ 537	200	
Scientific papers and publications in technical magazines			
Nº of scientific papers	5	10	DEC reporting
Nº of publications in technical magazines	2	3	
Practice abstracts			
Nº of practice abstracts	0	12	DEC reporting
Events			
Nº of events	18	10	DEC reporting
Nº of people reached	+ 102 711	1000	
Discussion forum & Workshops			
Nº of discussion forum	0	1/4	DEC reporting
Nº of people reached	0	10/40	
Final conference			
Nº of presentations	---	10	DEC reporting
Nº of invited speakers	---	3	
Nº of participants	---	50	
Partners' own dissemination channels			
Nº of mentions	115	100	DEC reporting
Nº of people reached	+38 000	500	
Cooperation with sister project and similar projects			
Nº of projects invited to collaborate	19	20	DEC reporting
Nº of activities initiated	8	5	
Nº of people reached	---	500	
Other KPIs			
Nº of brochure/leaflet/goodies distributed	1201	500	DEC reporting

